

Diversity of performance patterns in dairy goats: multi-scale analysis of the lactation curves of milk yield, body condition score and body weight

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12 **Abstract**

13 In the dairy goat sector, reduced longevity is a key issue leading to higher replacement
14 rates in the herd and a poor dilution of doe rearing costs. There is a need to better
15 understand the determinants of lifetime performance. Thus, the general objective of
16 this work was to analyze the phenotypic variability of lifetime trajectories (milk yield
17 (MY), body weight (BW) and body condition score (BCS)) through a 3-step approach:
18 (1) characterize individual phenotypic lactation curves, (2) explore the associations
19 between MY, BW and BCS curves at the lactation scale and (3) assess the diversity of
20 phenotypic curves over successive lactations. Routine data from two experimental
21 farms: Le Pradel (Dataset 1, Ardeche department, France) and MoSAR experimental
22 farm (Dataset 2, Yvelines department, France) were used. Dataset 1 included 793
23 Alpine goats from 1996 to 2020. Dataset 2 included 339 Alpine and 310 Saanen goats
24 from 2006 to 2022. Weekly MY records (Dataset 1) and daily MY records (Dataset 2)
25 were fitted using a lactation model with explicit representation of perturbations. Monthly
26 BW records (Dataset 1) and BCS record (Dataset 1&2) were fitted using the Grossman
27 multiphasic model. Daily BW records (Dataset 2) were fitted using a weight model.
28 Each individual lactation curve modelled for MY, BW and BCS was thus summarized
29 by synthetic indicators of level and dynamics. Principal component analysis was
30 performed on the MY, BW and BCS indicators separately, and clusters of phenotypic
31 curves identified. At the lactation scale, associations between MY, BW and BCS
32 clusters were evaluated by contingency tables with a chi-square test. Lifetime-scale
33 bar plots were used to display cluster changes throughout parities. For MY curves, 4
34 and 3 clusters were found for primiparous and multiparous goats respectively. For BW,
35 lumbar and sternal BCS curves, 3 clusters were found for all parities. At the lactation
36 scale, no major association was found among phenotypic curves suggesting a diversity
37 of energy partitioning strategies between life functions. At the lifetime scale, change
38 among clusters occurred primarily between first and second lactation, whereas a
39 pattern of stable cluster membership appeared for multiparous goats. Further analyses
40 are needed to include reproductive performance in analyzing lifetime performance
41 clusters, to better identify clusters or combinations of clusters at risk for culling.

42 **Key words:** Dairy goats, milk yield curves, body weight curves, body condition score
43 curves, lactation scale, lifetime scale

44 **Implications**

45 In the context of the sustainability of farming systems, finding management strategies
46 that improve animal robustness and efficiency is increasingly important. Among the
47 various facets of a robust goat, the balance between the capacity to produce milk and
48 manage body reserves is a key characteristic, implying to better understand the
49 associations between phenotypic curves of performance (e.g., milk yield, body weight,
50 body condition score). The present study showed that there were no major
51 associations between curve types at the lactation scale. At the lifetime scale, change
52 among clusters was more pronounced between first and second lactation, while a
53 stable pattern of cluster membership appeared in multiparous goats. Our results
54 challenge mainstream management strategies that are based on an average animal
55 performance. Considering the diversity of performance profiles can be a way to better
56 manage individuals or groups of individuals to improve their robustness.

57 **Introduction**

58 The dairy goat sector faces many challenges, such as animals with reduced longevity
59 (Palhière et al., 2018) and high replacement costs. In the future design of livestock
60 farming, breeding and managing robust animals is on the agenda of many research
61 programs. One of the key elements of robustness is to consider goats as a biological
62 system in which productive functions (e.g., lactation, growth, reproduction, etc...) dynamically
63 interact through complex mechanisms involving nutrient partitioning
64 (Bauman and Currie, 1980; Friggens et al., 2017). Nutrient partitioning implies that
65 energy cannot be maximized across all productive functions and therefore some
66 functions are given priority over others, especially to support some physiological
67 stages (e.g. lactation). Thus, individual variability in performance could reveal different
68 nutrient partitioning strategies. A first important aspect to explain changes in nutrient
69 partitioning is the succession of reproductive cycles throughout life. This modifies
70 priorities among functions to support a given physiological stage (e.g., gestation,
71 lactation). In addition to these homeorhetic drivers, priorities can be modified by various
72 aspects of the farming system environment. For instance, it is well documented that
73 genetic selection for milk production has altered priorities among functions in dairy
74 cattle leading to health and reproductive disorders (Pryce et al., 2001; Roche et al.,
75 2009; Friggens et al., 2010). Indeed, high genetic merit for milk has led to energy
76 partitioning in favor of lactation over other biological functions. It is also known that
77 priorities can be modified to cope with nutritional constraints. For instance, most of
78 female mammals will not invest energy in pregnancy during feed shortage (Friggens,
79 2003). As a central function to support lactation and as a buffer for variation in nutritional
80 environment, body reserves play a central role in energy partitioning among productive
81 functions.

82 Assessing the diversity of phenotypic lactation curves reflecting productive functions
83 (e.g., milk yield (MY) and body reserves (body weight (BW), body condition score
84 (BCS)) is a way to understand interactions among biological functions and potential
85 trade-offs between them. With time series data based on more frequent measures

86 (e.g., MY, BW, BCS...), the use of mathematical models can provide information about
87 individual phenotypic lactation curves and their variability. Models can be used to
88 transform raw data into biologically meaningful information. Over the past decades,
89 authors have proposed mathematical models to capture the shape of the lactation
90 curve (Wood, 1967; Cobby & Le Du, 1978; Dhanoa, 1981; Wilmink, 1987) and some
91 wanted to have models based on a biological framework (Dijkstra et al., 1997; Friggens
92 et al., 1999; Pollott, 2000). With more frequent data, a recent model was developed to
93 characterize the lactation curve with an explicit representation of perturbations (Ben
94 Abdelkrim et al., 2020). This model allows a better estimation of the lactation potential
95 for a given animal. Having an estimation of the potential lactation curve can help to
96 identify those goats that need improved feeding management (Arnal et al., 2018).
97 Studies on modelling the shape of BW or BCS curves through lactation (Macé et al.,
98 2023) are less frequent. Some mathematical functions with an exponential approach
99 (Sauvant et al., 2012) or a random regression approach (Berry et al., 2003) have been
100 used. In dairy cows, Ollion et al. (2016) developed a method to characterize trade-offs
101 among biological functions. This method was based on principal component analysis
102 (PCA) followed by agglomerative hierarchical classification (AHC) using MY curves,
103 BCS curves and reproductive performance.

104 Studying the diversity of lactation curve sequences on a lifetime scale opens the
105 perspective to look at potential changes in priorities among functions across the
106 lifespan, and thus to see how early lifetime performance can impact the subsequent
107 productive lifetime. Understanding the career diversity within a herd would allow the
108 development of management strategies adapted to different curve sequence types,
109 thereby favoring animal longevity. To our knowledge, no studies in dairy goats have
110 used models to compare milk, body weight and body condition dynamics at a lactation
111 scale or at a lifetime scale. In this study, we hypothesized that a multi-scale approach
112 (lactation and lifetime scale) based on phenotypic curves would bring insights on
113 energy partitioning strategies among biological functions. The general objective of this
114 work was to analyze the variability of lifetime phenotypic trajectories through a 3-step
115 approach: (1) characterize individual lactation curves, (2) explore the associations
116 between MY, BW and BCS curves at the lactation scale and (3) assess the diversity of
117 phenotypic curves over successive lactations.

118 **Material and methods**

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120 **Ethics approval**

121 This paper did not require animal experimentation approval because the datasets
122 came from routine data recorded on farm. The two farms, housed their animals in
123 conditions that fully complied with the current regulations on animal housing (directive
124 98/58/CE).

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129 **Datasets**

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131 *Dataset 1 (1996-2020).*

132 Data came from the experimental farm Le Pradel (agricultural high school Olivier de
133 Serres) located in the French department Ardeche (44° 34' 58.4364" N; 4° 29' 53.2068"
134 E). The data set contained 2,460 lactations from 793 Alpine goats including 93,965
135 weekly milk records, 28,099 monthly BW records and 26,271 monthly BCS records.
136 Over this period, goats were milked twice daily, and the recorded milk yield value was
137 the sum of the two milkings. BW was measured once a month on a weighing balance.
138 BCS was evaluated at lumbar and sternal regions on a 0 to 5 scale (Morand-Fehr and
139 Hervieu, 1999). Le Pradel farm had a seasonal system with a kidding period between
140 January and February. During the breeding season in August, inseminated goats
141 received a hormonal treatment. Males were introduced 18 days after artificial
142 insemination (AI). Males stayed until October to mate the goats that returned to heat
143 after AI and those that were not inseminated. Goats produced milk from January to
144 November-December. All lactations retained for milk records had a first record less
145 than 30 days after kidding, a last record after 240 days in milk and had less than 30
146 days interval between two records. All lactations retained for BW and BCS records had
147 a first record less than 17 days after kidding, a last record after 240 days, more than 8
148 records per lactation and less than 100 days interval between two records. Lactations
149 lasted on average 289.6 ± 28.5 days. The final dataset 1 concerned 2,271 lactations
150 for milk records, 1,935 lactations for BW records and 1,851 lactations for BCS records
151 (Table 1).

152 *Dataset 2 (2006-2022).*

153 Data came from the MoSAR experimental farm (INRAE-AgroParisTech) located in the
154 French department of Yvelines (48° 50' 31.4801" N; 1° 56' 56.5843" E). The data set
155 contained 1,608 lactations from 339 Alpine and 310 Saanen goats including 396,814
156 daily milk records, 252,725 daily BW records and 11,525 monthly BCS records. The
157 farm has a rotary parlor with an automatic weighing platform, goats were milked and
158 weighed twice a day. The recorded value for milk was the sum of the two milkings. The
159 recorded value for BW was an average of the two measurements. BCS was assessed
160 as the same way as in dataset 1. The MoSAR experimental farm had a seasonal
161 system with a kidding period between January and February. During the breeding
162 season in August, all goats received a hormonal treatment. Selected goats were
163 inseminated after treatment on a fixed date in August. For the goats that were naturally
164 mated, a male was introduced in small groups of 10-12 goats over 6-7 days. Goats
165 produced milk from January to November-December. All lactations retained for milk
166 records in our dataset had a first record less than 5 days after kidding, a last record
167 after 240 days in milk and had less than 30 days interval between two records. All
168 lactations retained for BW and BCS records had a first record less than 20 days after
169 kidding, a last record after 240 days, more than 8 records per lactation and less than
170 80 days interval between two records. Lactations lasted on average 280.1 ± 35.1 days.

171 The final dataset 2 concerned 1,256 lactations for milk records, 1,299 lactations for
 172 BW records and 381 lactations for BCS records (Table 1).

173 **Table 1.** Lactation selection criteria for milk yield, body weight and body condition score records with
 174 parity and breed distribution for dataset 1 and 2.

		Milk yield		Body weight		Body condition score	
		Dataset 1	Dataset 2	Dataset 1	Dataset 2	Dataset 1	Dataset 2
Lactation stage (d)	First record	<30	<5	<17	<20	<17	<20
	Last record	>240	>240	>240	>240	>240	>240
Interval between records (d)		<30	<30	<100	<80	<100	<80
Record per lactation		/	/	>=8	>=8	>=8	>=8
Parity	Primiparous	671	520	606	499	549	143
	Multiparous	1,600	736	1,329	800	1,302	238
Breed	Alpine	2,271	716	1,935	742	1,851	191
	Saanen	0	540	0	557	0	190
Total		2,271	1,256	1,935	1,299	1,851	381

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196 Models of individual phenotypic lactation curves

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198 Models were selected according to data frequency.

199 Lactation curve fitting of both daily and monthly data (dataset 1 and 2)

200 The perturbed lactation model proposed by Ben Abdelkrim et al. (2020) was fitted to
 201 the MY time-series data (Figure.1). This model was designed to decompose lactation
 202 dynamics into two components: a theoretical unperturbed lactation curve, and the
 203 perturbations in milk yield. This approach was selected to characterize lactation curves
 204 corrected for perturbations because it captures a proxy of the lactation potential. The
 205 model used for the unperturbed lactation was a modified version of the Wood model
 206 (Wood, 1967) integrating a late lactation decrease. The model was fitted in Scilab
 207 (Version 6.1.1, www.scilab.org) using an updated version (Martin,
 208 unpublished/personal communication) of the fitting protocol described in Ben
 209 Abdelkrim et al. (2020). For further details about the model and the fitting procedure
 210 see Appendix A, section 1.

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213 **Figure.1** Example of daily milk records fitted using the model proposed by Ben Abdelkrim et al. (2020)
 214 with empty white circles representing raw data, black bold lines representing the unperturbed lactation
 215 model (ULM), black thin lines representing the perturbed lactation model (PLM), and grey dotted lines
 216 representing the theoretical Wood model. The ULM trajectory was summarized with synthetic indicators:
 217 MY_{peak} = highest milk yield value; MY_{210} = milk yield value at 210 days; SumMY = sum of daily milk yield
 218 values over 250 days; Peak time = time of the highest milk yield value; Persistence = $(MY_{250} - MY_{150}) / MY_{150} \times 100$.
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BCS curve fitting of monthly data (dataset 1 and 2)

The triphasic model proposed by Grossman et al. (1999) was fitted to monthly BCS time-series data (Figure.2). This model was designed to decompose body condition dynamics into three parts: a depletion phase, a plateau phase and a repletion phase. This model allows characterization of curves with less frequent data (at least five records were needed). The model was fitted using RStudio (version 2023.06.01). For further details about the model and the fitting procedure see Appendix A, section 3.

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Figure. 2 Example of monthly sternal body condition records fitted using the model proposed by Grossman et al. (1999) with empty white circles representing raw data, black straight lines representing the fitted curve. This fitted curve was summarized with synthetic indicators: BCS_{S_k} = sternal BCS at kidding; $BCS_{S_{min}}$ = minimum sternal BCS; $BCS_{S_{210}}$ = sternal BCS at 210 days; $Dep_speed_{S_{k \rightarrow 30}}$: sternal BCS depletion speed between kidding and 30 days = $(BCS_{S_{30}} - BCS_{S_k}) / 30$; $Rep_speed_{S_{180 \rightarrow 210}}$: sternal BCS repletion speed between 180 and 210 days = $(BCS_{S_{210}} - BCS_{S_{180}}) / 30$.

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249 *BW curve fitting of daily data*

250 The unperturbed weight model proposed by Martin and Ben Abdelkrim, (2019) was
251 fitted to the daily BW time-series data from dataset 2 (Figure.3). This model was
252 designed to decompose the BW dynamics during a lactation into a sequence of
253 depletion/repletion of BW. This model was built to be flexible and to capture various
254 shapes of BW curves. The model was fitted using RStudio (version 2023.06.01). For
255 further details about the model and the fitting procedure see Appendix A section 2.
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258 **Figure. 3** Example of daily body weight records fitted using the model proposed by Martin and Ben
259 Abdelkrim, (2019) with empty white circles representing raw data, black straight lines representing the
260 fitted trajectory. This fitted trajectory was summarized with synthetic indicators: BW_k = body weight at
261 kidding; BW_{min} = minimum body weight; BW_{210} = body weight at 210 days; $Dep_speed_{k \rightarrow 30}$: Body weight
262 depletion speed between kidding and 30 days = $(BW_{30} - BW_k) / 30$; $Rep_speed_{180 \rightarrow 210}$: Body weight
263 repletion speed between 180 and 210 days = $(BW_{210} - BW_{180}) / 30$.

264 The same fitting procedure used for BCS was used to fit monthly BW data from dataset
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274 Fitting convergence

275 Non-convergence of the fitting procedure occurred in situations where the model was
 276 irrelevant to describe data. Non-convergence of the fitting procedure accounted for 0
 277 % of lactations of the datasets for MY, 3 % of lactations of the datasets for BW and 30
 278 % of lactations of the datasets for lumbar BCS and 22 % of lactations of the datasets
 279 for sternal BCS. Modelled curves with extreme features were removed using the
 280 Tukey's rule (Tukey, 1977) applied to estimates of model parameters and root mean
 281 square error (RMSE) (exclusion of values above the third quartile plus three times the
 282 interquartile range). Loss associated to extreme features accounted for 3 % of
 283 lactations of the datasets for MY, 7 % of lactations of the datasets for BW and 6 % of
 284 lactations of the datasets for lumbar and sternal BCS.

285 Synthetic indicators to describe fitted individual phenotypic lactation curves

286 Finally, we used synthetic indicators derived from modelled curves to describe
 287 lactation, BW and BCS curves during lactation. Two types of indicators were used:
 288 level indicators were considered to characterize performance at specific times and
 289 dynamic indicators were considered to characterize temporal changes in performance
 290 (Table 2).

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292 **Table 2.** Description of the set of synthetic indicators used to describe fitted individual phenotypic curve
 293 for milk yield (MY), body weight (BW) and body condition score (BCS).

Curve	Type ²	Indicator	Description and calculation	Unit
Milk production	L	SumMY	Total milk produced between 0 and 250 days of lactation, calculated as the sum of daily milk yield values	kg
	L	MY _{peak}	Highest daily milk yield reached during lactation	kg/d
	L	MY ₂₁₀	Daily milk yield at 210 days of lactation	kg/d
	D	Peak time	Lactation time at which the maximum milk yield value is reached	d
	D	Persistency	Rate of decrease of milk production between 150 and 250 days of lactation: $(MY_{250} - MY_{150}) / MY_{150} \times 100$	%
Body weight	L	BW _k	Daily body weight at kidding	kg
	L	BW _{min}	Minimum daily body weight reached during lactation	kg
	L	BW ₂₁₀	Daily body weight value at 210 days of lactation	kg
	D	Dep_speed _{k->30}	Speed of body weight depletion between 0 and 30 days of lactation, calculated as $(BW_{30} - BW_k) / 30$	kg/d
	D	Rep_speed _{180->210}	Speed of body weight repletion between 180 and 210 days of lactation, calculated as: $(BW_{210} - BW_{180}) / 30$	kg/d
Lumbar or sternal body condition score ¹	L	BCS_X _k	Lumbar/sternal BCS at kidding	[0-5] scale
	L	BCS_X _{min}	Minimum lumbar/sternal BCS reached during lactation	[0-5] scale
	L	BCS_X ₂₁₀	Lumbar/sternal BCS at 210 days of lactation	[0-5] scale
	D	Dep_speed_X _{k->30}	Speed of lumbar/sternal BCS depletion between 0 and 30 days of lactation, calculated as: $(BCS_{X_{30}} - BCS_{X_k}) / 30$	[0-5] scale/d
	D	Rep_speed_X _{180->210}	Speed of lumbar/sternal BCS repletion between 180 and 210 days of lactation, calculated as: $(BCS_{X_{210}} - BCS_{X_{180}}) / 30$	[0-5] scale/d

¹ X stands for lumbar (L) or sternal (S).

² L = level; D = dynamic.

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295 **Statistical analysis**

296 *Clusters of phenotypic curves at lactation scale*

297 All statistical analyses were performed using RStudio (version 2023.06.01). Data and
298 scripts can be found in the repository linked to this manuscript (Gafsi et al., 2023). To
299 characterize groups of individual phenotypic curves, principal component analysis
300 (PCA) was performed on the synthetic indicators of MY, BW and BCS separately. The
301 number of principal components (PC) was based on the cumulative variance. To
302 choose the number of PCs at least 75 % of the total variance was needed. PCA was
303 followed by an agglomerative hierarchical clustering (AHC) based on the retained
304 number of PCs for each of MY, BW and BCS, using Ward's linkage procedure. Ward's
305 method is a hierarchical procedure that iteratively merges groups of individuals
306 represented by points in a Euclidean space resulting in the smallest increase in the
307 sum of within-group sums of squares. This clustering method produces groups that
308 minimize intra-group dispersion and maximize inter-group dispersion at each binary
309 fusion. Preliminary analysis was conducted including the farming systems, breed, and
310 parities all together. Breed and farming systems did not play a strong role on cluster
311 characterization. Parity played a strong role in cluster characterization for MY and BW.
312 So, we performed a clustering by parity (primiparous vs. multiparous) for MY and BW,
313 whereas we performed a single clustering for all parities together for BCS. The optimal
314 number of clusters was based on the higher relative loss of inertia criteria. Differences
315 between clusters for each synthetic indicator were assessed using a one-way ANOVA
316 followed by a Tukey test.

317 *At lactation scale, contingency tables between clusters of phenotypic curves*

318 To assess the associations between MY, BW and BCS curves at the lactation scale,
319 we produced two-way contingency tables. After clustering, each lactation was
320 assigned a MY, BW or BCS cluster. A contingency table summarized the conditional
321 frequencies of two clusters (e.g., MY and BW clusters). It was used to assess if a
322 cluster membership for a given phenotypic curve was associated to a particular cluster
323 membership for another phenotypic curve, i.e. it showed how these two clusters were
324 dependent on each other. MY, BW and BCS records concerned different numbers of
325 lactations, so each contingency table (e.g., MY with BW or MY with lumbar BCS)
326 considered different sub-populations. Chi-squared tests were performed to assess for
327 associations, between phenotypic curves. Cramer's V test was performed on
328 significant associations to evaluate the strength of the associations. Cramer's V values
329 ranged from 0 to 1. Values close to 1 indicate a strong association, whereas values
330 close to 0 indicate a weak association.

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335 *At lifetime scale, changes in cluster composition for each parity*

336 To assess the diversity of phenotypic lactation curves at lifetime scale, we produced
 337 bar plots of the composition of each cluster for parity n in terms of clusters in the next
 338 parity $n+1$. With this visual display, it is possible to characterize if goat's assignment to
 339 a cluster is stable across parities (reflecting goats with a stable type of lactation curve
 340 across parities) or if assignment to a cluster varies across parities (reflecting goats with
 341 various dynamics during their lifetime). Chi-squared tests were performed to assess
 342 for associations between lactation curves. Cramer's V test was performed on
 343 significant associations to evaluate the strength of the associations.

344 **Results**

345 *Goodness-of-fit*

346 For the two data sets, the RMSE averaged $5.0\% \pm 1.9\%$ of the average MY per
 347 lactation, $2.7\% \pm 1.0\%$ of the average BW per lactation, $3.6\% \pm 1.6\%$ of the average
 348 lumbar BCS per lactation, and $3.1\% \pm 1.3\%$ of the average sternal BCS per lactation.

349 *Phenotypic lactation curves characterization*

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351 For all clusters of MY, BW and BCS, a detailed description of cluster names is given
 352 in table 3.

353 **Table 3.** Detailed description of cluster names for MY, BW and BCS. The upper script letter describes
 354 the phenotype (Y: milk yield; W: body weight; LU: lumbar BCS and ST: sternal BCS). The superscript
 355 describes if the cluster is for primiparous (p) or multiparous (m) goats. The subscript describes the key
 356 feature of the cluster (letter for level and plus or minus sign for dynamics).

Phenotypic curve	Cluster	
	Primiparous	Multiparous
MY ¹	Y ^p _{L+} = Low MY and high persistency. Y ^p _{L-} = Low MY and low persistency. Y ^p _{M-} = Medium MY and low persistency. Y ^p _H = High MY and medium persistency.	Y ^m _{M+} = Medium MY and high persistency. Y ^m _{M-} = Medium MY and low persistency. Y ^m _H = High MY and medium persistency.
BW	W ^p _{L-} = Low BW and low depletion. W ^p _{H+} = High BW and high depletion. W ^p _{H-} = High BW and low depletion.	W ^m _{L-} = Low BW and low depletion. W ^m _{H+} = High BW and high depletion. W ^m _{H-} = High BW and low depletion.
	All parities	
Lumbar BCS	LU _{M+} = Medium lumbar BCS and depletion. LU _M = Medium lumbar BCS and low depletion. LU _{H+} = High lumbar BCS and depletion.	
Sternal BCS	ST _{M+} = Medium sternal BCS and depletion. ST _M = Medium sternal BCS and low depletion. ST _{H+} = High sternal BCS and depletion.	

¹Abbreviations: MY = milk yield; BW = body weight; BCS = body condition score

357 Clusters of MY lactation curves

358 The first two PCs accounted for 83.5 % of the total variance for primiparous goats and
 359 81.6 % for multiparous goats. The first PC captured the total amount of milk produced
 360 during the lactation and accounted for 53.1 % of the total variance for primiparous
 361 goats and 50.7 % for multiparous goats. The second PC captured the persistency and
 362 peak time of the lactation curve and accounted for 30.4% of the total variance for
 363 primiparous goats and 30.8 % for multiparous goats. Based on the highest loss of
 364 inertia, four clusters were retained for primiparous goats, and three clusters were
 365 retained for multiparous goats (Figure.4).

392 **Figure.4** PCA and clusters of milk yield synthetic indicators in primiparous (a) and multiparous (b) goats
 393 with grey circles representing raw data, lines representing the mean cluster and dotted lines
 394 representing a paragon cluster (i.e., the most representative goat in the cluster) (MY_{peak} = highest milk
 395 yield value; MY_{210} = milk yield value at 210 days; SumMY = sum of daily milk yield values over 250 days;
 396 Peak time = time of the highest milk yield value; Persistency = $(MY_{250} - MY_{150} / MY_{150}) \times 100$; Y_{L+}^P = Low
 397 milk yield and high persistency cluster for primiparous; Y_{L-}^P = Low milk yield and low persistency cluster
 398 for primiparous; Y_{M-}^P = Medium milk yield and low persistency cluster for primiparous; Y_{H}^P = High milk
 399 yield and medium persistency cluster for primiparous; Y_{M+}^m = Medium milk yield and high persistency
 400 cluster for multiparous; Y_{M-}^m = Medium milk yield and low persistency cluster for multiparous; Y_{H}^m =
 401 High milk yield and medium persistency cluster for multiparous).

402 Full details for each cluster are given in tables 4a and 4b.

403 Primiparous clusters were characterized by:

- 404 - a group of low persistency clusters with two different total milk production levels
- 405 (63.3% of the primiparous): a low-level cluster (Y^{P_L-}) that produced 155.6 kg less
- 406 over the lactation than a medium-level cluster (Y^{P_M-}).
- 407 - a medium persistency cluster with the highest total milk production level that
- 408 gathered 22.6% of the primiparous (Y^{P_H}).
- 409 - the highest persistency cluster with a low total milk production level that
- 410 gathered 14.1% of the primiparous ($Y^{P_{L+}}$).

411 **Table 4a.** Statistical description of synthetic indicators for MY clusters in primiparous goats.

Indicator	Y^{P_L-} ³ n = 273	$Y^{P_{L+}}$ n = 163	Y^{P_M-} n = 459	Y^{P_H} n = 262	Pooled SE	p-value ²
SumMY ¹	629.1 ^a	675.5 ^b	784.7 ^c	925.4 ^d	67.2	***
MY _{peak}	3.0 ^a	3.0 ^a	3.7 ^b	4.2 ^c	0.4	***
MY ₂₁₀	2.1 ^a	2.7 ^b	2.6 ^b	3.4 ^c	0.3	***
Peak time	47.4 ^a	106.0 ^b	49.8 ^a	71.4 ^c	26.7	***
Persistency	-36.7 ^a	-19.2 ^b	-35.2 ^a	-27.2 ^c	10.9	***

^{a-d} Means with superscripts differ significantly by row.

¹ SumMY = sum of daily milk yield values over 250 days; MY_{peak} = highest milk yield value; MY₂₁₀ = milk yield value at 210 days; Peak time = time of the highest milk yield value; Persistency = $(MY_{250} - MY_{150} / MY_{150}) \times 100$.

² p-value resulting from Tukey's test assessing the significance of differences between profiles for each variable. NS (p<0.1), *(p<0.05); and ***(p≤0.001).

³ $Y^{P_{L+}}$ = Low milk yield and high persistency cluster; Y^{P_L-} = Low milk yield and low persistency cluster; Y^{P_M-} = Medium milk yield and low persistency cluster; Y^{P_H} = High milk yield and medium persistency cluster.

412

413 Multiparous clusters were characterized by:

- 414 - a group of medium total milk production levels with two different persistency
- 415 (65.4 % of the multiparous): a high persistency cluster ($Y^{m_{M+}}$) that maintained
- 416 20.4 % more the production than a low persistency cluster ($Y^{m_{M-}}$).
- 417 - the highest total milk production level cluster with a medium persistency (Y^{m_H})
- 418 that gathered 34.6 % of the population.

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427 **Table 4b.** Statistical description of synthetic indicators for MY clusters in multiparous goats.

Indicator	$Y^{m_{M+}}$ ³ n = 741	$Y^{m_{M-}}$ n = 740	Y^{m_H} n = 783	Pooled SE	p-value ²
SumMY ¹	911.4 ^a	940.9 ^b	1,212.4 ^c	111.5	***
MY _{peak}	4.1 ^a	4.7 ^b	5.7 ^c	0.6	***
MY ₂₁₀	3.4 ^a	2.9 ^b	4.1 ^c	0.5	***
Peak time	71.1 ^a	38.1 ^b	58.3 ^c	27.4	***
Persistence	-25.9 ^a	-46.3 ^b	-36.3 ^c	12.4	***

^{a-c} Means with superscripts differ significantly by row.

¹ SumMY = sum of daily milk yield values over 250 days; MY_{peak} = highest milk yield value; MY₂₁₀ = milk yield value at 210 days; Peak time = time of the highest milk yield value; Persistence = $(MY_{250} - MY_{150} / MY_{150}) \times 100$.

² p-value resulting from Tukey's test assessing the significance of differences between profiles for each variable. NS (p<0.1), *(p<0.05); and ***(p≤0.001).

³ $Y^{m_{M+}}$ = Medium milk yield and high persistency cluster; $Y^{m_{M-}}$ = Medium milk yield and low persistency cluster; Y^{m_H} = High milk yield and medium persistency cluster.

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430 With respect to farm, for primiparous goats, Pradel's Alpine goats, Grignon's Alpine
 431 goats, and Grignon's Saanen goats were more represented in the $Y^{p_{M-}}$ cluster because
 432 this is the cluster with the highest number of goats overall. For multiparous goats,
 433 Pradel's Alpine goats were more represented in the Y^{p_H} cluster, whereas Grignon's
 434 Alpine goats were less represented in this cluster. Grignon's Saanen goats were more
 435 represented in the $Y^{m_{M+}}$ cluster. See Appendix B section 1 for more details.

436

437

438 Clusters of BW lactation curves

439

440 The first two PCs accounted for 77.4% of the total variance for primiparous goats and
 441 79.4% for multiparous goats. The first PC represented the level of BW at different times
 442 of lactation and accounted for 52.8% of the total variance for primiparous goats and
 443 56.9% for multiparous goats. The second PC represented the BW speed loss in the 30
 444 days after kidding and accounted for 24.7% of the total variance for primiparous goats
 445 and 22.5% for multiparous goats. Three clusters were retained for each parity group
 446 due to the highest loss of inertia (Figure.5).

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453 (a) Variables - PCA

463 (b) Variables - PCA

473 **Figure.5** PCA and clusters of body weight synthetic indicators in primiparous (a) and multiparous (b)
 474 goats with grey circles representing raw data, lines representing the mean cluster and dotted lines a
 475 paragon cluster (i.e., the most representative goat in the cluster) (BW_k = body weight at kidding; BW_{min}
 476 = minimum body weight; BW_{210} = body weight at 210 days; $Dep_speed_{k \rightarrow 30}$: Body weight depletion speed
 477 between kidding and 30 days = $(BW_{30} - BW_k) / 30$; $Rep_speed_{180 \rightarrow 210}$: Body weight repletion speed
 478 between 180 and 210 days = $(BW_{210} - BW_{180}) / 30$; W_{L-}^p = Low body weight and low depletion cluster in
 479 primiparous; W_{H+}^p = High body weight and high depletion cluster in primiparous; W_{H-}^p = High body
 480 weight and low depletion cluster in primiparous; W_{L-}^m = Low body weight and low depletion cluster in
 481 multiparous; W_{H+}^m = High body weight and high depletion cluster in multiparous; W_{H-}^m = High body
 482 weight and low depletion cluster in multiparous).

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488 Full details for each cluster are given in tables 5a and 5b.

489 Primiparous clusters were characterized by:

- 490 - a group of low depletion clusters with two different BW level at kidding (68.6%
491 of the primiparous): a low-level cluster (**W^P_L**) that averaged 10.0 kg less at
492 kidding than a high-level cluster (**W^P_H**). Those profiles had a higher BW₂₁₀ than
493 BW_k.
- 494 - the highest depletion cluster with a high BW level at kidding (**W^P_{H+}**) that gathered
495 31.4% of the population. Despite having the highest repletion speed, this cluster
496 presented a lower BW₂₁₀ than BW_k due to the high level of depletion, that is not
497 totally compensated at 210 days of lactation.

498

499 **Table 5a.** Statistical description of synthetic indicators for BW clusters in primiparous goats.

Indicator	W ^P _L ³ n = 418	W ^P _{H+} n = 312	W ^P _{H-} n = 264	Pooled SE	p-value ²
BW _k ¹	47.7 ^a	54.3 ^b	57.7 ^c	4.0	***
BW _{min}	45.2 ^a	47.6 ^b	55.6 ^c	3.5	***
BW ₂₁₀	49.5 ^a	52.9 ^b	61.5 ^c	4.3	***
Dep_speed _{k->30}	-0.05 ^a	-0.17 ^b	-0.03 ^c	0.07	***
Rep_speed _{180->210}	0.04 ^a	0.06 ^b	0.05 ^c	0.03	***

^{a-c} Means with superscripts differ significantly by row.

¹ BW_k = body weight at kidding; BW_{min} = minimum body weight; BW₂₁₀ = body weight at 210 days; Dep_speed_{k->30} = (BW₃₀ - BW_k) / 30; Rep_speed_{180->210} = (BW₂₁₀ - BW₁₈₀) / 30.

² p-value resulting from Tukey's test assessing the significance of differences between profiles for each variable. NS (p<0.1), *(p<0.05); and ***(p≤0.001).

³ W^P_L = Low body weight and low depletion cluster; W^P_{H+} = High body weight and high depletion cluster; W^P_{H-} = High body weight and low depletion cluster.

500

501 Multiparous clusters were characterized by:

- 502 - a group of low depletion clusters with two different BW level at kidding (73.4 %
503 of the multiparous): a low-level (**W^m_L**) that averaged 17.6 kg less at kidding than
504 a high-level cluster (**W^m_H**). For these clusters BW₂₁₀ was lower than BW_k.
- 505 - the highest depletion cluster with a high BW level at kidding (**W^m_{H+}**) that
506 gathered 26.6% of the multiparous. Despite having the highest repletion speed,
507 this profile presented a lower BW₂₁₀ than BW_k due to the high level of depletion,
508 that is not totally compensated at 210 days of lactation.

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515 **Table 5b.** Statistical description of synthetic indicators for BW clusters in multiparous goats.

Indicator	W^{m_L} ³ n = 835	$W^{m_{H+}}$ n = 513	W^{m_H} n = 583	Pooled SE	p-value ²
BW_k ¹	64.1 ^a	78.1 ^b	81.7 ^c	6.2	***
BW_{min}	57.8 ^a	65.5 ^b	74.2 ^c	5.2	***
BW_{210}	61.1 ^a	69.4 ^b	76.2 ^c	5.4	***
$Dep_speed_{k \rightarrow 30}$	-0.14 ^a	-0.35 ^b	-0.14 ^a	0.12	***
$Rep_speed_{180 \rightarrow 210}$	0.04 ^a	0.04 ^b	0.01 ^c	0.03	***

^{a-c} Means with superscripts differ significantly by row.

¹ BW_k = body weight at kidding; BW_{min} = minimum body weight; BW_{210} = body weight at 210 days; $Dep_speed_{k \rightarrow 30}$ = $(BW_{30} - BW_k) / 30$; $Rep_speed_{180 \rightarrow 210}$ = $(BW_{210} - BW_{180}) / 30$.

² p-value resulting from Tukey's test assessing the significance of differences between profiles for each variable. NS ($p < 0.1$), * ($p < 0.05$); and *** ($p \leq 0.001$).

³ W^{m_L} = Low body weight and low depletion cluster; $W^{m_{H+}}$ = High body weight and high depletion cluster; W^{m_H} = High body weight and low depletion cluster.

516

517 For primiparous goats, Pradel's Alpine goats were more represented in the W^{p_L} - and
 518 $W^{p_{H+}}$ clusters. Grignon's Alpine goats were more represented in the W^{p_L} - cluster.
 519 Grignon's Saanen goats were more represented in the W^{p_H} - cluster. For multiparous
 520 goats, Pradel's Alpine goats and Grignon's Alpine goats were more represented in the
 521 W^{m_L} - cluster. Grignon's Saanen goats were more represented in the W^{m_H} - cluster. See
 522 Appendix B section 2 for more details.

523

524 Clusters of BCS lactation curves

525

526 For lumbar and sternal BCS, clusters were built all parities together. For lumbar BCS,
 527 the first two PCs accounted for 75.8% of the total variance. The first PC represented
 528 levels of lumbar score at different times of the lactation ($BCS_{L_{min}}$ and BCS_{L_k}) and
 529 accounted for 46.9% of the total variance. The second PC represented the lumbar BCS
 530 speed loss in the 30 days after kidding and accounted for 28.9% of the total variance.
 531 Three clusters were retained due to the highest loss of inertia. For sternal BCS, the
 532 first two PCs represented 78.6% of the total variance. The first PC represented levels
 533 of sternal score at different times of the lactation ($BCS_{S_{min}}$ and $BCS_{S_{210}}$) and
 534 accounted for 50.7% of the total variance. The second PC represented the sternal BCS
 535 speed loss in the 30 days after kidding and accounted for 27.9% of the total variance.
 536 Three clusters were retained due to the highest loss of inertia (Figure.6).

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Figure.6 PCA and clusters of lumbar (a) and sternal (b) body condition score synthetic indicators with grey circles representing raw data, lines representing the mean cluster and dotted lines a paragon cluster (i.e., the most representative goat in the cluster) (BCS_{L_k} = lumbar BCS at kidding; BCS_{L_{min}} = minimum lumbar BCS; BCS_{L₂₁₀} = lumbar BCS at 210 days; Dep_speed_{L_k→30}: lumbar BCS depletion speed between kidding and 30 days = (BCS_{L₃₀} - BCS_{L_k}) / 30; Rep_speed_{L₁₈₀→210}: lumbar BCS repletion speed between 180 and 210 days = (BCS_{L₂₁₀} - BCS_{L₁₈₀}) / 30; BCS_{S_k} = sternal BCS at kidding; BCS_{S_{min}} = minimum sternal BCS; BCS_{S₂₁₀} = sternal BCS at 210 days; Dep_speed_{S_k→30}: sternal BCS depletion speed between kidding and 30 days = (BCS_{S₃₀} - BCS_{S_k}) / 30; Rep_speed_{S₁₈₀→210}: sternal BCS repletion speed between 180 and 210 days = (BCS_{S₂₁₀} - BCS_{S₁₈₀}) / 30; LU_{M+} = Medium lumbar body condition score and depletion cluster; LU_M = Medium lumbar body condition score and low depletion cluster; LU_{H+} = High lumbar body condition score and depletion cluster; ST_{M+} = Medium sternal body condition score and depletion cluster; ST_M = Medium sternal body condition score and low depletion cluster; ST_{H+} = High sternal body condition score and depletion cluster).

578

579 Full details for each cluster are given in tables 6 and 7.

580 Lumbar BCS clusters were characterized by:

- 581 - a group of depletion clusters with two different lumbar BCS level at kidding (68.7
- 582 % of the population): a medium level cluster (**LU_{M+}**) that averaged 0.4 points
- 583 less at kidding than a high-level cluster (**LU_{H+}**). LU_{M+} profile presented the
- 584 highest repletion speed and the lowest minimum lumbar BCS value.
- 585 - the lowest depletion cluster with a medium lumbar BCS level at kidding that
- 586 gathered 31.3% of the population (**LU_M**). LU_M cluster presented the same
- 587 repletion speed than LU_{H+}.
- 588

589 **Table 6.** Statistical description of synthetic indicators for lumbar BCS clusters in goats.

590

Indicator	LU _{M+} ³ n = 437	LU _M n = 459	LU _{H+} n = 572	Pooled SE	p-value ²
BCS_L _k ¹	2.5 ^a	2.4 ^b	2.9 ^c	0.2	***
BCS_L _{min}	2.1 ^a	2.3 ^b	2.6 ^c	0.2	***
BCS_L ₂₁₀	2.3 ^a	2.5 ^b	2.7 ^c	0.2	***
Dep_speed_L _{k→30}	-0.009 ^a	0.002 ^b	-0.006 ^c	0.005	***
Rep_speed_L _{180→210}	0.002 ^a	0.001 ^b	0.001 ^b	0.001	***

^{a-c} Means with superscripts differ significantly by row.

¹ BCS_L_k = lumbar BCS at kidding; BCS_L_{min} = minimum lumbar BCS; BCS_L₂₁₀ = lumbar BCS at 210 days; Dep_speed_L_{k→30} = (BCS_L₃₀ - BCS_L_k) / 30; Rep_speed_L_{180→210} = (BCS_L₂₁₀ - BCS_L₁₈₀) / 30.

² p-value resulting from Tukey's test assessing the significance of differences between profiles for each variable. NS (p<0.1), *(p<0.05); and ***(p≤0.001).

³ LU_{M+} = Medium lumbar body condition score and depletion cluster; LU_M = Medium lumbar body condition score and low depletion cluster; LU_{H+} = High lumbar body condition score and depletion cluster.

591

592 Sternal BCS profiles were characterized by:

- 593 - a group of depletion clusters with two different sternal BCS level at kidding (56.5
- 594 % of the population): a medium-level cluster (**ST_{M+}**) that averaged 0.7 points
- 595 less at kidding than a high-level cluster (**ST_{H+}**). ST_{M+} cluster presented the
- 596 lowest minimum sternal BCS. These clusters presented the highest and the
- 597 same repletion speed.
- 598 - the lowest depletion cluster with a medium sternal BCS level at kidding that
- 599 gathered 43.5 % of the population (**ST_M**). ST_M cluster presented the lowest
- 600 repletion speed.

601

602

603

604 **Table 7.** Statistical description synthetic indicators for sternal BCS clusters in goats.

605

Indicator	ST _{M+} ³ n = 489	ST _M n = 708	ST _{H+} n = 433	Pooled SE	p-value ²
BCS_S _k ¹	3.0 ^a	3.1 ^b	3.7 ^c	0.2	***
BCS_S _{min}	2.5 ^a	2.9 ^b	3.2 ^c	0.2	***
BCS_S ₂₁₀	2.6 ^a	3.0 ^b	3.4 ^c	0.2	***
Dep_speed_S _{k→30}	-0.010 ^a	-0.003 ^b	-0.010 ^a	0.006	***
Rep_speed_S _{180→210}	0.0020 ^a	0.0004 ^b	0.0020 ^a	0.001	***

^{a-c} Means with superscripts differ significantly by row.

¹ BCS_S_k = sternal BCS at kidding; BCS_S_{min} = minimum sternal BCS; BCS_S₂₁₀ = sternal BCS at 210 days; Dep_speed_S_{k→30} = (BCS_S₃₀ - BCS_S_k)/ 30; Rep_speed_S_{180→210} = (BCS_S₂₁₀ - BCS_S₁₈₀)/ 30.

²p-value resulting from Tukey's test assessing the significance of differences between profiles for each variable. NS (p<0.1), *(p<0.05); and ***(p<0.001).

³ST_{M+} =Medium sternal body condition score and depletion cluster; ST_M =Medium sternal body condition score and low depletion cluster; ST_{H+} =High sternal body condition score and depletion cluster.

606

607 For lumbar BCS, Pradel's Alpine goats were more represented in the LU_{H+} cluster,
 608 whereas Grignon's Alpine goats were more represented in the LU_M cluster. Grignon's
 609 Saanen goats were more represented in the LU_M cluster. Primiparous represented
 610 between 30 % and 38 % of the population in each profile for lumbar BCS. For sternal
 611 BCS, Pradel's Alpine goats were more represented in the ST_M cluster, whereas
 612 Grignon's Alpine goats were more represented in the ST_{H+} cluster. Grignon's Saanen
 613 goats were more represented in the ST_{H+} cluster. Primiparous represented between
 614 30 % and 35 % of the population in each profile for sternal BCS. See Appendix B
 615 section 3 for more details.

616

617 *Diversity of phenotypic curves at lactation scale*
 618 *Associations between MY curves and BW curves*

619

620 In this section, the association between MY and BW is presented. For primiparous
 621 goats, the association between MY and BW clusters is shown in Table 8a. The Chi²
 622 test was significant (P<0.001) with a Cramer's V of 0.17. The association Y^{P_{M-}} with W^{P_{L-}}
 623 accounted for the highest proportion of goats with 17.8 % of the population, followed
 624 by the associations Y^{P_{L-}} with W^{P_{L-}} and Y^{P_{M-}} with W^{P_{H+}} with 13.9 % of the population. The
 625 association Y^{P_{L+}} with W^{P_{H+}} accounted for the lowest proportion of goats with 2.8 % of
 626 the population. The remaining 51.6% of the population was almost equally distributed
 627 among the clusters.

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633 **Table 8a.** Contingency table displaying the frequency of individual primiparous goats affected to MY
634 and BW clusters (see section 2 for clustering methodology).

Milk yield profile	Body weight profile						Total	
	W ^p _L - ²		W ^p _{H+}		W ^p _{H-}		n	%
	n	% ¹	n	%	n	%		
Y ^p _L - ²	124	13.9	45	5.0	43	4.8	212	23.7
Y ^p _{L+}	44	4.9	25	2.8	44	4.9	113	12.7
Y ^p _{M-}	159	17.8	124	13.9	77	8.6	360	40.3
Y ^p _H	60	6.7	86	9.6	62	6.9	208	23.3
Total	387	43.3	280	31.4	226	25.3	893	100.0

¹ % = proportion of goats among the 893 primiparous goats.

² Y^p_{L+}= Low milk yield and high persistency cluster; Y^p_{L-}= Low milk yield and low persistency cluster; Y^p_{M-}= Medium milk yield and low persistency cluster; Y^p_H= High milk yield and medium persistency cluster; W^p_{L-}= Low body weight and low depletion cluster; W^p_{H+}= High body weight and high depletion cluster; W^p_{H-}= High body weight and low depletion cluster.

635

636 For multiparous goats, the association between MY and BW clusters is shown in Table
637 8b. The Chi² test was significant (P<0.001) with a Cramer's V of 0.17. The association
638 Y^m_{M+} with W^m_{L-} accounted for the highest proportion of goats with 18.6% of the
639 population. The association Y^m_{M+} with W^m_{H+} accounted for the lowest proportion of
640 goats with 5.6 % of the population. The remaining 75.8 % of the population was almost
641 equally distributed among the clusters.

642 **Table 8b.** Contingency table displaying the frequency of individual multiparous goats affected to MY
643 and BW clusters (see section 2 for clustering methodology).

Milk yield profile	Body weight profile						Total	
	W ^m _L - ²		W ^m _{H+}		W ^m _{H-}		n	%
	n	% ¹	n	%	n	%		
Y ^m _{M+} ²	313	18.6	95	5.6	145	8.6	553	32.8
Y ^m _{M-}	242	14.4	166	9.9	140	8.3	548	32.5
Y ^m _H	169	10.0	200	11.9	215	12.8	584	34.7
Total	724	43.0	461	27.4	500	29.7	1,685	100.0

¹ % = proportion of goats among the 1,685 multiparous goats.

² Y^m_{M+}= Medium milk yield and high persistency cluster; Y^m_{M-}= Medium milk yield and a low persistency cluster; Y^m_H= High milk yield and a medium persistency cluster; W^m_{L-}= Low body weight and low depletion cluster; W^m_{H+}= High body weight and high depletion profile cluster; W^m_{H-}= High body weight and low depletion cluster.

644

645 The conclusions were the same for the associations between MY and lumbar BCS
 646 curves and for the associations between MY and sternal BCS curves see Appendix C
 647 section 1 and 2.

648 *Associations between BW and sternal BCS curves*

649

650 In this section, the association between BW and sternal BCS is presented. For
 651 primiparous goats, the association between BW and sternal BCS clusters is shown in
 652 Table 9a. The Chi² test was significant (P<0.001) with a Cramer's V of 0.25. The
 653 association W^{P_{L-}} with ST_{M+} and W^{P_{H+}} with ST_M accounted for the highest proportion of
 654 goats with 18.8 % of the population, followed by the association W^{P_{L-}} with ST_M with
 655 17.9 % of the population. The association W^{P_{H-}} with ST_{M+} accounted for the lowest
 656 proportion of goats with 1.6 % of the population. The remaining 42.9 % of the
 657 population was almost equally distributed among the clusters.

658 **Table 9a.** Contingency table displaying the frequency of individual primiparous lactations affected
 659 to BW and sternal BCS clusters (see section 2 for clustering methodology).

	Sternal BCS profile						Total	
	ST _{M+} ²		ST _M		ST _{H+}		n	%
Body weight profile	n	% ¹	n	%	n	%	n	%
W ^{P_{L-}}	84	18.8	80	17.9	24	5.4	188	42.0
W ^{P_{H+}}	75	16.7	84	18.8	29	6.5	188	42.0
W ^{P_{H-}}	7	1.6	29	6.5	36	8.0	72	16.0
Total	166	37.1	193	43.1	89	19.9	448	100.0

¹ % = proportion of goats among the 448 primiparous goats.

²W^{P_{L-}} = Low body weight and low depletion cluster; W^{P_{H+}} = High body weight and high depletion cluster;
 W^{P_{H-}} = High body weight and low depletion cluster; ST_{M+} =Medium sternal body condition score and
 depletion cluster; ST_M =Medium sternal body condition score and low depletion cluster; ST_{H+} =High
 sternal body condition score and depletion cluster.

660

661 For multiparous goats, the association between BW and sternal BCS clusters is shown
 662 in Table 9b. The Chi² test was significant (P<0.001) with a Cramer's V of 0.18. The
 663 association W^{m_{L-}} with ST_M accounted for the highest proportion of goats with 18.6 % of
 664 the population, followed by the association W^{m_{L-}} with ST_{M+} with 14.2 % of the
 665 population. The association W^{m_{H-}} with ST_{M+} accounted for the lowest proportion of
 666 goats with 2.8 % of the population. The remaining 64.4 % of the population was almost
 667 equally distributed among the clusters.

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675 **Table 9b.** Contingency table displaying the frequency of individual multiparous lactations affected to
 676 BW and BCS sternal clusters (see section 2 for clustering methodology).

	Sternal BCS profile						Total	
	ST _{M+} ²		ST _M		ST _{H+}		n	%
Body weight profile	n	% ¹	n	%	n	%	n	%
W ^m _{L-} ²	139	14.2	182	18.6	74	7.6	395	40.5
W ^m _{H+}	120	12.3	132	13.5	93	9.5	345	35.3
W ^m _{H-}	27	2.8	115	11.8	94	9.6	236	24.2
Total	286	29.3	429	44.0	261	26.7	976	100.0

¹ % = proportion of goats among the 976 multiparous goats.

² W^m_{L-} = Low body weight and low depletion cluster; W^m_{H+} = High body weight and high depletion cluster; W^m_{H-} = High body weight and low depletion cluster; ST_{M+} = Medium sternal body condition score and depletion cluster; ST_M = Medium sternal body condition score and low depletion cluster; ST_{H+} = High sternal body condition score and depletion cluster.

677

678 The conclusions were the same for the associations between BW and lumbar BCS
 679 curves see Appendix C section 3.

680 *Association between lumbar and sternal BCS curves*

681

682 For primiparous goats, the association between lumbar and sternal BCS clusters is
 683 shown in Table 10a. The Chi² test was significant (P<0.001) with a Cramer's V of 0.27.
 684 The association LU_{M+} with ST_{M+} accounted for the highest proportion of goats with 21.4
 685 % of the population, followed by the association LU_{H+} with ST_M with 19.5 % of the goats.
 686 The association LU_M with ST_{M+} accounted for the lowest proportion of goats with 6.7 %
 687 of the population. The remaining 52.4 % of the population was almost equally
 688 distributed among the clusters.

689 **Table 10a.** Contingency table displaying the frequency of individual primiparous lactations affected to
 690 BCS lumbar and BCS sternal clusters (see section 2 for clustering methodology).

	Sternal BCS profile						Total	
	ST _{M+} ²		ST _M		ST _{H+}		n	%
Lumbar BCS profile	n	% ¹	n	%	n	%	n	%
LU _{M+} ²	80	21.4	31	8.3	28	7.5	139	37.2
LU _M	25	6.7	51	13.6	30	8.0	106	28.3
LU _{H+}	27	7.2	73	19.5	29	7.8	129	34.5
Total	132	35.3	155	41.4	87	23.3	374	100.0

¹ % = proportion of goats among the 374 primiparous goats.

²LU_{M+} = Medium lumbar body condition score and depletion cluster; LU_M = Medium lumbar body condition score and low depletion cluster; LU_{H+} = High lumbar body condition score and depletion cluster; ST_{M+} = Medium sternal body condition score and depletion cluster; ST_M = Medium sternal body condition score and low depletion cluster; ST_{H+} = High sternal body condition score and depletion cluster.

691 For multiparous goats, the association between lumbar and sternal BCS clusters is
 692 shown in Table 10b. The Chi² test was significant (P<0.001) with a Cramer's V of 0.35.
 693 The association LU_{M+} with ST_{M+} accounted for the highest proportion of goats with 20.0
 694 % of the population, followed by the association LU_{H+} with ST_M with 18.6 % of the goats.
 695 The association LU_{M+} with ST_{H+} accounted for the lowest proportion of goats with 4.1
 696 % of the population. The remaining 57.3 % of the population was almost equally
 697 distributed among the clusters.

698 **Table 10b.** Contingency table displaying the frequency of individual multiparous lactations affected to
 699 lumbar and sternal BCS clusters (see section 2 for clustering methodology).

Lumbar BCS profile	Sternal BCS profile						Total	
	ST _{M+} ²		ST _M		ST _{H+}		n	%
	n	% ¹	n	%	n	%	n	%
LU _{M+} ²	148	20.0	52	7.0	30	4.1	230	31.1
LU _M	59	8.0	108	14.6	45	6.1	212	28.6
LU _{H+}	36	4.9	138	18.6	124	16.8	298	40.3
Total	243	32.8	298	40.3	199	26.9	740	100.0

¹ % = proportion of goats among the 740 multiparous goats.

²LU_{M+} = Medium lumbar body condition score and depletion cluster; LU_M = Medium lumbar body condition score and low depletion cluster; LU_{H+} = High lumbar body condition score and depletion cluster; ST_{M+} = Medium sternal body condition score and depletion cluster; ST_M = Medium sternal body condition score and low depletion cluster; ST_{H+} = High sternal body condition score and depletion cluster.

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Diversity of phenotypic lactation curves at lifetime scale

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MY lactation curves throughout parities

718 Individual lactation transition in MY curves between successive lactations is shown in
719 Figure.7. Between parity 1 to 4, the Chi² test was significant (P<0.001) with a Cramer's
720 V ranging from 0.27 to 0.32. For primiparous goats, almost half of the goats in the Y^{P_H}
721 cluster remained the most productive ones in parity 2 (Y^{m_H}), while the other half
722 switched to other clusters. More than half of the goats in the two lowest productive
723 clusters (Y^{P_{L-}} and Y^{P_{L+}}) switched to the Y^{m_{M+}} cluster. Goats in the Y^{P_{M+}} cluster were
724 almost equally distributed among the clusters in parity 2. For multiparous goats, more
725 than two third of the goats in the Y^{m_H} cluster remained in this cluster in successive
726 lactations. The proportion of goats that remained in the Y^{m_{M-}} cluster in successive
727 lactations increased with parity. Goats in the Y^{m_{M+}} cluster were almost equally
728 distributed among the clusters in successive lactations.

746 **Figure .7** Barplots displaying the frequency of goats affected to a MY cluster between (a) parity 1 and
747 2, (b) parity 2 and 3 , (c) parity 3 and 4 (Y^{P_{L+}}= Low milk yield and high persistency cluster for primiparous;
748 Y^{P_{L-}}= Low milk yield and low persistency cluster for primiparous; Y^{P_{M-}} = Medium milk yield and low
749 persistency cluster for primiparous; Y^{P_H} = High milk yield and medium persistency cluster for
750 primiparous; Y^{m_{M+}}= Medium milk yield and high persistency cluster for multiparous; Y^{m_{M-}}= Medium milk

751 yield and low persistency cluster for multiparous; Y^{m_H} = High milk yield and medium persistency cluster
 752 for multiparous).

753 BW lactation curves throughout parities

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755 Individual lactation transition in BW curves between successive lactations is shown in
 756 Figure.8. Between parity 1 and 4, the χ^2 test was significant ($P < 0.001$) with a
 757 Cramer's V ranging from 0.41 to 0.44. For primiparous, goats in the W^{p_H} - cluster
 758 switched clusters in parity 2. More than 80% of the goats in the $W^{p_{H+}}$ and in the W^{p_L} -
 759 clusters switched to the W^{m_L} -cluster in parity 2. For multiparous, more than two third of
 760 the goats in the W^{m_H} - cluster remained in this cluster in successive lactations. Half of
 761 the goats in the $W^{m_{H+}}$ cluster remained in this cluster, while the other half switched
 762 clusters in successive lactations. Half of the goats in the W^{m_L} - cluster remained in this
 763 cluster, while the other half switched clusters in successive lactations.

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783 **Figure .8** Barplots displaying the frequency of goats affected to a BW cluster between (a) parity 1 and
 784 2, (b) parity 2 and 3 , (c) parity 3 and 4 (W^{p_L} = Low body weight and low depletion cluster; $W^{p_{H+}}$ = High
 785 body weight and high depletion cluster; W^{p_H} = High body weight and low depletion cluster; W^{m_L} = Low
 786 body weight and low depletion cluster; $W^{m_{H+}}$ = High body weight and high depletion cluster; W^{m_H} = High
 787 body weight and low depletion cluster).

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789 BCS lactation curves throughout parities

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791 Only sternal BCS is presented here. Individual lactation transition in sternal BCS
 792 curves between successive lactations is shown in Figure.9. Between parity 1 and 4,
 793 Chi² test was significant (P<0.001) with a Cramer's V ranging from 0.35 to 0.49. For
 794 primiparous, more than half of the goats in the three clusters remained in their cluster
 795 in parity 2, while the other part switched to other clusters. For multiparous, more than
 796 three quarters of the goats in the ST_{H+} profile remained in this cluster in successive
 797 lactations, while the other part switched to other clusters. More than half of the goats
 798 in the ST_{M+} and ST_M profile remained in their cluster in successive lactations, while the
 799 other part switched to other clusters.

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Figure .9 Barplots displaying the frequency of goats affected to a sternal BCS cluster between (a) parity 1 and 2, (b) parity 2 and 3 and (c) parity 3 and 4 (ST_{M+} =Medium sternal body condition score and depletion profile; ST_M =Medium sternal body condition score and low depletion profile; ST_{H+} = High sternal body condition score and depletion profile).

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823

824 **Discussion**

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826 Our dataset is relatively large and the frequency of measurement of the different
827 variables is high. However, it reflected only the management of two farms. The
828 observations made here are a starting point for a better understanding of the
829 relationships between milk production, body condition score and body weight in goats,
830 but will need to be confirmed in various systems. In addition, it will be necessary to add
831 reproductive performance, which is also considered when making decisions about
832 culling.

833 The first objective of this work was to characterize the diversity of phenotypic curves
834 of performance (MY, BW, BCS) at the lactation scale.

835 *MY curves*

836 For MY curves we found four clusters for primiparous goats and three clusters for
837 multiparous goats. Parity had a strong effect on the scale of the lactation curve. Over
838 the lactation, primiparous had lower total milk yield than multiparous goats (Gipson and
839 Grossman, 1990). Parity also affected the shape of the lactation curve. For all parities,
840 some clusters presented the same shape characterized by a low persistency with
841 different milk production levels (Y^{pL-} , Y^{pM-} , Y^{mM-}). These clusters, in terms of shape,
842 were close to the mean curve of cluster 2, which represented the most common shape
843 of lactation observed by Arnal et al. (2018) over the French dairy goat population. This
844 cluster 2 represented 39 % of the French dairy goat population, characterized by a
845 marked peak and a medium persistency, i.e. a low persistency for our study because
846 Arnal et al. had an additional atypical cluster with a very low persistency. For
847 primiparous goats, one cluster combined a low level of milk with the highest persistency
848 over the whole population (Y^{pL+}). This is consistent with observations made by Gipson
849 and Grossman, (1990), where persistency was the highest in primiparous goats and
850 decreased when parity increased. This can be explained by a lower level of
851 development of the mammary gland (Safayi et al., 2010). This shape of lactation curve
852 was also observed in the study of Arnal et al. (2018). However, persistency and MY
853 are not always negatively correlated, because for all parities we observed that the
854 highest productive clusters were those with a medium persistency (Y^{pH} , Y^{mH}) rather
855 than those with the lowest persistency. This result is close to the finding of Arnal et al.
856 (2018) that their highest productive cluster had a high persistency. We can hypothesize
857 that better fed goats produce more milk and are better able to maintain that production.

858 Despite differences between Saanen and Alpine goats being reported in the literature
859 (Gipson and Grossman, 1990; Rupp et al., 2011; Arnal et al., 2018), breed did not have
860 a significant effect on the scale or the shape of the lactation curves in the present study,
861 regardless of parity. It should be noted that the two breeds were only present on one
862 farm (Grignon) and thus had the same feeding and management environment.

863 *Lactation curves of BW*

864 For BW curves we found three clusters for primiparous and multiparous goats. Parity
865 and breed played a strong role on the scale of BW curves. As expected, primiparous

866 goats were lighter than multiparous ones. For all parities, we found low depletion
867 clusters (W^{pL-} , W^{mL-} , W^{pH-} , W^{mH-}) and high depletion clusters (W^{pH+} , W^{mH+}). The low
868 depletion clusters had the same shape but differed in terms of level. Only the high
869 depletion clusters differed in terms of shape from the other clusters. However, the
870 depletion speed was lower in primiparous goats than in multiparous goats. Indeed, for
871 primiparous goats, the difference between kidding and the minimum of BW averaged
872 3.7 kg, while for multiparous this difference averaged 8.3 kg. These results are
873 consistent with what Sauviant et al. (2012) observed when they modelled the BW curve
874 by parity. They observed that primiparous were lighter and lost less BW (4.0 kg on
875 average) than multiparous goats (7.3 kg on average). To our knowledge, little work has
876 been done to characterize BW curves in dairy goats. Our work can be compared to the
877 study of Macé et al. (2019) in meat sheep. They analyzed BW longitudinal data in 1146
878 ewes to characterize curves over multiple production cycles. Most of their curves had
879 the same shape but differed in terms of level.

880 All multiparous clusters had a higher BW at kidding (BW_k) than at the beginning of the
881 subsequent gestation (BW_{210}). In contrast, for primiparous clusters the opposite was
882 mainly true, indicating that primiparous goats were still growing in first lactation. For
883 multiparous and for all clusters BW_k was higher than BW_{210} at the end of lactation. BW
884 is easy to measure on farm to monitor animals, especially to quantify energy balance
885 (Thorup et al., 2012). However, BW measures also include digestive content, growth,
886 gravid uterus and body reserves. Therefore, BW measures alone are not consistent
887 enough to quantify body reserve changes. They need to be analyzed with BCS to better
888 understand body reserves dynamics.

889 A breed effect was observed for BW curves: Saanen goats were more represented in
890 the high-level clusters for all parities (W^{pH-} , W^{mH-}). They were generally heavier than
891 Alpine goats (Sauviant et al., 2012).

892 *Lactation curves of BCS*

893 For lumbar and sternal BCS we found three clusters for all parities. First for all parities,
894 we found high depletion clusters for lumbar (LU_{M+} , LU_{H+}) and sternal (ST_{M+} , ST_{H+}) BCS.
895 Then, we found low depletion clusters for lumbar (LU_M) and sternal (ST_M) BCS. High
896 depletion clusters presented the same shape but differed in terms of level. Only the
897 low depletion clusters differed in terms of shape. These results are also consistent with
898 the observations of Macé et al. (2019). They found the same shape but differing in
899 terms of level. Moreover, for the high depletion clusters, the variation between kidding
900 and the minimum of BCS averaged 0.4 points for LU_{M+} , 0.3 points for LU_{H+} , and 0.5
901 points for ST_{M+} and ST_{H+} . Our values, especially for sternal BCS, are lower but close
902 to those described in the French feeding system (Inra, 2018).

903 Parity did not significantly affect BCS curves. Indeed, primiparous goats represented
904 a third of the whole population in each of the clusters. Breed did not significantly affect
905 BCS curves. We observed only a farm effect on BCS because Grignon's Alpine and
906 Saanen goats were more represented in the LU_M - and ST_{H+} clusters. This can probably
907 be explained by differences in the personnel carrying out the BCS evaluation (although
908 differences in herd management, or a random distribution linked to the clustering
909 approach cannot be excluded).

910 *A great diversity of associations among biological functions*

911 The second objective of this work was to assess the diversity of associations among
912 the different phenotypic curves. We investigated whether one phenotypic curve was
913 associated with another. At the lactation scale, the Chi² test was significant for
914 associations but the Cramer's V showed weak to moderate values (globally less than
915 0.4) (Kotrlík et al., 2011). This lack of strong associations among lactation curves of
916 MY, BW and BCS suggests there exists a relatively large diversity of energy
917 partitioning strategies among individuals. Associations among MY, BW and BCS were
918 well-studied in dairy cows. Some studies showed a positive correlation between pre-
919 calving BCS and milk production (Waltner et al., 1993; Roche et al., 2007), whereas
920 other studies did not find any relationship between these variables (Garnsworthy and
921 Topps, 1982; Garnsworthy and Jones, 1987). More recently, Ollion et al. (2016)
922 assessed the diversity of trade-offs between milk production, body reserves and
923 reproduction in early lactation dairy cows. They showed four different trade-off profiles
924 according to a priority given to a biological function. The first trade-off profile
925 represented cows giving priority to lactation instead of reproduction, the second trade-
926 off profile represented cows giving priority to reproduction instead of lactation. The third
927 trade-off profile represented cows with poor performances in all functions, and the last
928 trade-off profile represented cows with no trade-off among functions. All of these
929 approaches considered correlations between traits at one time point and not at the
930 whole lactation scale. Moreover, these performance traits were evaluated at the
931 beginning of the lactation where cows exhibited a negative energy balance allowing
932 energy partitioning in favor of milk over body reserves. Another possible explanation
933 for the lack of strong associations found in our study is that trade-off between life
934 functions, and therefore correlations between traits, are well expressed when animals
935 face feed shortage (Blanc et al., 2006; Friggens et al., 2017). Our data came from two
936 experimental farms where we can assume that animals are well managed and not so
937 constrained in terms of nutrition.

938 The diversity of associations among biological functions found in the present study
939 could also suggest a great diversity in intake at the individual level. However, we are
940 not able today to accurately evaluate individual intake. Furthermore, BCS was used as
941 a proxy to evaluate body reserve dynamics. As a subjective evaluation of body
942 reserves, BCS was probably not accurate enough to capture a relationship with MY.
943 MY fat would have been important to consider, because at equal MY fat could vary a
944 lot. However, this variable was not considered in our study because although some
945 data were available, the frequency was low (less than one measurement per month).
946 On the one hand, this diversity of biological profiles can be seen as a potential resource
947 to improve farming system resilience (Dumont et al., 2020). On the other hand, this
948 diversity raises questions about feeding systems that assumed a relationship between
949 a BW and a MY curve. There is a need to better quantify body reserves contribution in
950 terms of energy to goat's requirements (Inra, 2018). These findings question
951 management strategies that are based on the average animal, i.e; ignoring cluster
952 types. A perspective can be to adapt management strategies to the diversity of
953 individual profiles in terms of phenotypic curves and then better match animal's
954 requirements.

955 The final objective of this work was to assess the diversity of phenotypic curves at the
956 lifetime scale. For each phenotypic trait, the Chi^2 test was significant. Cramer's V test
957 showed lower values for MY than for BW and BCS suggesting stronger associations
958 for BW and BCS. For MY curves, we saw for primiparous goats that almost half of the
959 goats in the Y^{p_H} cluster remained in this cluster in parity 2, while the lowest productive
960 goats (Y^{p_L-} and $Y^{p_{L+}}$) switched cluster in parity 2. For multiparous, we observed a more
961 stable pattern of cluster membership with two thirds of the goats in the Y^{m_H} cluster
962 remaining in this cluster in successive lactations. Usually, milk production increases
963 from first to fourth parity. After the fourth parity, the level of milk production decreases
964 (Arnal et al., 2018). However, with genetic improvement, we can make the hypothesis
965 that some goats can reach their milk potential earlier. Goats that stayed in the highest
966 productive clusters could be animals that have reached their milk potential relatively
967 early. Goats that are changing clusters could be the ones that have not reached their
968 potential early. For BW curves across parities, we saw that for primiparous goats, most
969 of the goats in the W^{p_L-} remained in the lowest BW cluster (W^{m_L-}) in parity 2, while $W^{p_{H+}}$
970 switched to the W^{m_L-} cluster. Goats in the $W^{p_{H+}}$ presented the highest depletion speed,
971 so they were not able to recover from the intense depletion and remained in the lowest
972 cluster in parity 2. For multiparous goats, we also observed a pattern of cluster
973 membership, with more than three-quarters of the goats in the W^{m_H-} profile remaining
974 in this cluster in successive lactations. Half of the goats in the W^{m_L-} remained in this
975 cluster in successive lactations. For sternal BCS curves across parities, we saw that
976 more than half of the primiparous goats in the three clusters remained in their cluster
977 in parity 2. For multiparous goats, we observed that three-quarters of the goats in the
978 ST_{H+} cluster remained in this cluster in successive lactations. More than half of the
979 goats in the ST_{M+} and ST_M remained in their cluster in successive lactations. These
980 observations on BW and BCS over successive lactations, are consistent with what
981 Macé et al. (2019) observed in meat sheep. They observed one-third up to half of ewes
982 remaining in the same trajectory during successive cycles of production. They
983 supposed that changes in profile distribution could be linked to litter size that can play
984 a role in body weight depletion. We did not consider the prolificacy of the goats in our
985 study. This information was missing for 35% of the animals. When the number of kids
986 was known (single kid for 33% of the goats, two kids for 51%, three kids and more for
987 16%), we did not find any relationship with our clusters. However, it is an information
988 to consider in further analysis as it is described to be a factor related to milk production
989 (Hayden et al., 1979; Zamuner et al., 2020). These results highlighted the importance
990 of a lifetime approach to better understand potential changes in priorities among
991 functions and see how an early lifetime performance can impact the whole productive
992 lifespan (Puillet and Martin, 2017). Lifetime and longevity approaches are increasingly
993 being studied because in France from 1991 to 2011, the female productive life
994 decreased by 346 days, which led to an average productive lifespan of 2.7 years per
995 goat (Palhière et al., 2018), which increases replacement costs.

996 *A methodology to analyze trade-off between phenotypic curves with heterogeneous* 997 *data frequency*

998 This methodology was built to analyze the trade-off between phenotypic lactation
999 curves based on longitudinal data with different frequencies. We used models adapted
1000 to the data frequency to better characterize our curves. However, this approach implied
1001 the creation of synthetic indicators to have the same baseline for phenotypic curves
1002 characterized by different models. For MY curves, synthetic indicators were simple to

1003 find, because we used common indicators to summarize a lactation curve with level
1004 and dynamic indicators such as the MY_{peak} , Peak time and Persistency. However,
1005 because the BW (dataset 1) and BCS data were less frequent (datasets 1 and 2) less
1006 elaborate models were used. This then meant that a more simple set of summary
1007 indicators was used to characterize these curves, which may not be as informative as
1008 those for MY. With heterogeneity in frequencies, it is difficult to use the same models
1009 to capture phenotypic curves. Differences in frequencies could lead to use simple
1010 models with parameters that are not always biologically meaningful. Or it may lead to
1011 the use of more complex models that deal with problems of parameters identifiability.
1012 It is important to find a way to use biologically meaningful parameters from different
1013 models as inputs for a clustering approach. This approach with model parameters will
1014 help to summarize the phenotypic curves without considering synthetic indicators.

1015 *Further development and potential use of on-farm record for managing animal*

1016 With development of on-farm automatic measuring technologies, more frequent data
1017 for MY or BW are becoming available. Some authors developed methods to
1018 characterize new indicators such as the deviation of milk production from a theoretical
1019 potential production (Ben Abdelkrim et al., 2020; Poppe et al., 2020; Adriaens et al.,
1020 2021). Intense and rapid MY or BW losses might be used as indicators of disease or
1021 metabolic disorders. Being able to identify these animals is of great interest for farming
1022 management. In our study, we used specific models that dissociated the effects of
1023 perturbation from a theoretical unperturbed curve. To characterize phenotypic curves,
1024 we focused only on unperturbed curves, which represented the potential production
1025 that an animal could have in a non-perturbed environment. With unperturbed MY and
1026 BW curves we saw a diversity of associations, it would be of future interest to also
1027 consider perturbations. The extent to which there are common perturbations on MY
1028 and BW curves may be informative. This approach has been used in dairy cows where
1029 Ben Abdelkrim et al. (2021) identified common perturbations in MY and BW. Using
1030 perturbations in a trajectory analysis could help to select animals that better cope with
1031 their environment.

1032 Data acquisition for BCS is more complicated in goats than in dairy cows. Manual BCS
1033 evaluation provided satisfactory results but is still a subjective method depending on
1034 the operator (Lerch et al., 2021). Recent studies have shown that new methods such
1035 as 3-dimension imaging did not provide satisfactory estimators of body composition
1036 and further developments may be needed to develop a robust phenotyping tool (Lerch
1037 et al., 2021). For all parities, BCS curves were well discriminated one month after
1038 kidding and stayed constant over the whole lactation. This observation suggests that
1039 BCS measures frequency can be reduced to key periods (kidding period, two months
1040 before breeding period, dry-off). This paper is the first step of a study that will include
1041 reproductive success in the analysis. Including reproduction outcome will help to
1042 predict fertility according to phenotypic curves for a given lactation. This analysis will
1043 be conducted also on the lifetime scale to look for potential unfavorable clusters. These
1044 further analyses will clarify this diversity of phenotypic curves and will provide metrics
1045 to better manage at-risk animals in terms of reproduction (e.g., finding the best periods
1046 to monitor at-risk animals). In the dairy goat sector, extended lactations became an
1047 alternative farming management to reduce culling and give another chance for a goat

1048 to reproduce. Being able to make early decisions on reproductive management, can
1049 be of economic interest and may increase sustainability (Adriaens et al., 2020).

1050 **Conclusion**

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1052 With a multi-scale approach on MY, BW and BCS time-series data, it was possible to
1053 characterize the diversity of associations between phenotypic lactation curves related
1054 to milk production and the use of body reserves. For each of MY, BW and BCS, the
1055 lactation curves clustered into 4 (MY) or 3 (BW, BCS) clusters. The diversity of
1056 associations at the lactation scale between clusters suggests a diversity of energy
1057 partitioning strategies among goats, which may provide different adaptive responses
1058 to environmental perturbations. Our results challenge mainstream management
1059 strategies that are based on average animal profiles. Rather, considering diversity of
1060 performance profiles can be a way to better adapt management to individuals or groups
1061 of individuals to improve their robustness. At the lifetime scale, change among clusters
1062 are more pronounced between first and second lactation, while a stable pattern of
1063 cluster membership appears for multiparous goats. Indeed, more than two thirds of the
1064 highest clusters for each phenotypic curve remained in these clusters in successive
1065 lactations. To further identify some clusters or combination of clusters that are at risk
1066 of culling, a first perspective of this study is to combine reproductive performance with
1067 MY, BCS and BW curves and then provide metrics to better manage animals at risk of
1068 culling.

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1084 **Appendices**

1085 Appendices are deposited on Zenodo with this following doi : [10.5281/zenodo.10090604](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10090604)

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1095

1096 **Data, scripts, code, and supplementary information availability**

1097 Data and scripts/code are deposited on Recherche Data Gouv with this following doi
1098 : <https://doi.org/10.57745/C1XPQ2>

1099 **Conflict of interest disclosure**

1100 The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts
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